

Tribological Behavior of Ultrananocrystalline Diamond (UNCD) Thin Films by Varying their Growth Conditions

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Abstract: Unique microstructured ultrananocrystalline diamond (UNCD) films are in high demand for several applications including tribology. In this film, wide range of microstructural modifications are possible which tailors the friction and wear properties of films [1,2]. The UNCD films were grown on mirror polished silicon (100) substrates using microwave plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition system. The deposition was carried out employing either (a) CH₄(1%)/Ar or (b) CH₄(6%)/N₂ plasma media with optimized deposition parameters [1]. Two different microstructures of UNCD films were thus obtained using such a distinct plasma media. Tribological properties of these films were studied considering sliding speed as one of variable parameter. The film deposited in CH₄(1%)/Ar showed friction value in the range of 0.15-0.25. This value was reduced to 0.02-0.1 for film deposited in CH₄(6%)/N₂ plasma media. Low friction in this film was mainly associated to negligible lifetime of run-in behavior. This was explained by large volume fraction of grain boundary which occupies the sp² short-range crystalline phase existing with sp³ bonded ultranano diamond grains [1,2]. Moreover, high wear resistance of these films is inherent property which is related to chemically inert surface. Furthermore, low wear of zirconia ball sliding against CH₄(6%)/N₂ film was related to soft-hard interaction across film-ball contact interfaces [1]. The wear depth of the film was negligible in both the conditions (up to 80 nm) [1,2].

Figure 1. Sliding speed dependent friction behavior in UNCD films deposited in: (a) CH₄ (1%)/Ar and (b) CH₄(6%)/N₂ plasma; Tribology parameters: Ball: ZrO₂ (dia. 6 mm), Load: 2 N, Condition: ambient atmospheric. Wear parameters also shown in inset.

Keywords

UNCD film, Sliding speed dependence, Tribological study

Reference

1. Revati Rani et al, RSc Adv. 5 (2015) 100663.
2. Revati Rani et al, Diam. Relat. Mater. 78 (2017) 12.